

Studies on Indan Acids as Potential Oral Hypoglycemic Agents.

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Indan acids, structurally related to hypoglycemic indole acids, were prepared and screened for hypoglycemic activity. Some of these acids were found to exhibit appreciable activity both in normal and in alloxan-diabetic animals. The highest activity was observed in compounds containing monomethoxy substituent in the benzenoid part of the indan moiety.

INDAN ring moiety having a peculiar combination of two benzylic protons was reported to possess significant pharmacological potentialities and by suitable structural variation it was found to exhibit various pharmacological responses¹. Lahiri *et al.*² reported significant oral hypoglycemic activity among a number of simple and methoxy substituted indanamines. A logical extension of the above work, was to explore

Chemistry

These indanacids were mostly prepared by the cyclodehydration of the corresponding simple and substituted aryl alkanedioic acids by either scheme I or II. Since in some cases, the above generalised procedure fails such acids were prepared using anhydrous aluminium chloride. Methoxy substitution at the para position makes the compound further resistant to

hypoglycemic activity among various synthetic intermediates of indanamines, in order to ascertain whether indan ring system alone or a combination of the functional group or groups are essential for hypoglycemic activity. Thus, indanamides—the synthetic precursors of indanamines were also reported to exhibit some activity³.

Again, a number of compounds containing acid functions were reported to exhibit appreciable hypoglycemic activity⁴⁻⁷. Moreover, reported significant hypoglycemic activity among a number of indole acids^{4, 8a, 8b}, gave further impetus to take up a systematic investigation of hypoglycemic activity among a series of indanacids, structurally related to active indanamines. Thus, the object of the present work is to explore the possibilities of using these simpler derivatives as oral hypoglycemic agents.

cyclisation to the corresponding indan acid leading to extremely low yield and in some cases resulted in the formation of products unrelated to these indan acids. However, all other mono- and dimethoxy substituted products were formed in reasonably high yield by the above generalised procedure.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds synthesised were primarily screened for hypoglycemic activity on normal healthy male rabbits by a procedure described earlier² and the potent ones on alloxan-diabetic rabbits. Diabetes was produced by the intravenous administration of alloxan-monohydrate (BDH) at a dose of 150 mg/kg in a 3.5% solution in acidified distilled water of pH 4.5^{9a, 9b}. The animals were kept on fasting for 18 hours and after taking the venous blood, the drug was administered as

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a 0.5% C.M.C. suspension through a stomach tube at a dose of 200 mg per kg. of body weight. The blood glucose concentration was followed at a regular interval of 3 hr following dosing upto 24 hr or even more. In normal animals the blood sugar fall was gradual over a period of 6-12 hr and was maintained even after 24 hr or more. Diabetic animals showed a greater variation in blood sugar concentration while in severely diabetic animals this variation was very erratic and in most cases without any response, indicating the insulin dependent nature of these compounds. All these compounds showed peak hypoglycemic response between 6-12 hr and the activity was maintained upto 24 hr or more. It seems rational to suppose that probably these compounds are either slowly absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract or are held by a strong plasma protein binding in blood or else they undergo biotransformation to an active metabolite whose elimination pattern is also very similar. The pK value of these acids are all very near the normal physiological pH of the blood and the compounds containing a carbonyl function are in general slightly more acidic and less active than their saturated carboxy analogs. It is also evident from Table I that the monomethoxy substituted products are all active but further methoxy substitution is not beneficial as dimethoxy compounds are less active while nonmethoxy compounds are the least active. In a given series reduced acids are more active than their keto analogs but that generalization does not hold good in case of *m*-methoxy substituted products. The effect of methoxy substitution, thus seems to be of prime importance so far as biological activity of these acids is concerned.

Indan-3-one-1-carboxylic acid (I)—Phenylsuccinic acid¹⁰ was cyclised with anhydrous AlCl₃ to give I in 61% yield; m.p. 120° (anhyd.)¹¹. (Found; C, 68.31; H, 4.60 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₀H₈O₃; C, (8.19; H, 4.55 per cent).

Indan-1-carboxylic acid (II)—I was reduced with zinc amalgam and conc. HCl to give II in 56% yield with m.p. 55°–56°¹². (Found; C, 74.20; H, 6.10 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₀O₂; C, 74.08; H, 6.17 per cent).

6-Methoxyindan-3-one-1-carboxylic acid (III)—Ethyl *m*-methoxy phenyl-benzalmalonate (IIIa) (b.p. 170–180° at 10–15 mm) (38 g) was treated with alcoholic KCN (16 g; 0.25 mole) and on hydrolysis with conc. HCl (sp. gr. 1.18; 120 ml) for 3 hr. gave *m*-methoxyphenyl succinic acid (IIIb) in 75% yield having m.p. 181.5°–182°. The above ester IIIa was prepared in excellent yield from *m*-methoxybenzaldehyde (13.6 g; 0.1 mole), ethylmalonate (16.0 g; 0.11 mole) and piperidine (1.0 ml) using benzene as solvent.

Finely powdered acid IIIb (50 g) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid (PPA) (750 g) either (i) by direct heating at 120° for 10 min or (ii) on boiling water bath for 4 hr. with stirring. The deep red reaction mixture was poured on ice and extracted with chloroform. On crystallisation after solvent removal, it gave the keto acid (III) in 65% yield with m.p. 187°–188.5°. (Found: C, 64.18; H, 4.80 percent. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₀O₄; C, 64.07; H, 4.85 percent).

TABLE I.—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND BIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF INDAN ACIDS

A

B

Compd. No.	Type	Compound	m.p. °C (Crystallising solvent)	pK ^c	Av. % Fall of Blood Sugar ^a	
					In normal ^b intact rabbits	In alloxan ^b diabetic rabbits
I	A	X=Y=H; n=0	120(H ₂ O)	6.21	12.47±1.02	
II	B	X=Y=H; n=0	55-56(H ₂ O)	6.55	17.40±3.08	
III	A	X=OCH ₃ ; Y=H; n=0	187-188.5 (H ₂ O)	6.32	20.02±2.05	28.15±3.04
IV	B	X=OCH ₃ ; Y=H; n=0	121-123 (C ₆ H ₆)	6.58	22.35±1.44	28.80±2.95
V	A	X=Y=OCH ₃ ; n=0	190-191 (H ₂ O)	6.40	15.66±1.07	
VI	B	X=Y=OCH ₃ ; n=0	114-115 (C ₆ H ₆)	6.69	14.05±1.19	
VII	A	X=Y=H; n=1	153-155 (H ₂ O)	6.34	9.75±2.35	
VIII	B	X=Y=H; n=1	55-56 (dil. Alc.)	6.54	16.26±3.14	
IX	A	X=OCH ₃ ; Y=H; n=1	151-153 (Alc. + H ₂ O)	6.44	21.85±2.09	32.32±4.30
X	B	X=OCH ₃ ; Y=H; n=1	97-98 (C ₆ H ₆)	6.73	22.80±1.34	31.65±3.40
XI	A	X=Y=OCH ₃ ; n=1	175-177 (H ₂ O)	6.48	17.22±3.10	
XII	B	X=Y=OCH ₃ ; n=1	159.5-161 (50% Alc.)	6.74	19.20±1.43	25.41±3.18

^aBlood sugar was determined by following the procedure of Jensen and Hagedorn¹³.

^bData on eight rabbits.

^cpK values determined spectrophotometrically with a Beckman DU 2 Spectrophotometer kept at 25°.

Experimental

All melting points are corrected and were determined in a Gallenkamp type apparatus. Boiling points are uncorrected.

6-Methoxyindan-1-carboxylic acid (IV)—III (15 g) was reduced with zinc amalgam (50 g) and conc. HCl to yield 70-75% of IV; m.p. 121°–123°. (Found. C, 68.60; H, 6.28 percent. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₂O₃; C, 68.76; H, 6.25 percent).

5, 6-Dimethoxyindan-3-one-1-carboxylic acid (V)—3, 4-Dimethoxyphenyl succinic acid¹⁹ was cyclised with PPA to give V in 80% yield; m. p. 190°-191° (dec.)^{2b}; (Found: C, 61.20; H, 5.14 percent. Calc. for C₁₂H₁₂O₅: C, 61.02; H, 5.09 percent),

5, 6-Dimethoxyindan-1-carboxylic acid (VI)—Clemmensen reduction of V gave VI in 65-70% yield; m.p. 114°-115°.^{2b} (Found: C, 64.81; H, 6.22 percent. Calc. for C₁₃H₁₄O₄; C, 64.86; H, 6.31 percent).

Indan-3-one-1-acetic acid (VII)—Finely powdered β-phenylglutaric acid¹⁴ (50 g) was treated with PPA (500 g) either (i) by direct heating at 120° for 10 min. or (ii) on boiling water bath for 3 hr with stirring. After addition to ice, the precipitated crude keto compound (VII) was crystallised from water in 56-70% and 71-75% yield respectively having m. p. 15°-55°. (Found: C, 69.33; H, 5.30 percent. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₀O₃; C, 69.47; H, 5.26 percent). This PPA method was found to be better than the usual AlCl₃ method¹⁵ so far as yield, ease of isolation and simplicity of operation are concerned.

Indan-1-acetic acid (VIII)—Clemmensen reduction of VII gave VIII in 70-75% yield with m. p. 55°-56°¹⁶. (Found: C, 75.23; H, 6.70 percent. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₂O₂; C, 75.01; H, 6.82 percent).

6-Methoxyindan-3-one-1-acetic acid (IX)—*m*-Methoxyphenylglutaric acid¹⁷ (50 g) was cyclised with PPA (1000 g) either (i) by direct heating at 120° for 10 min or (ii) on boiling water bath for 4 hr with stirring. The method of isolation was same as described earlier. The yield of the keto acid (IX) was 65% and m. p. 151°-153°. (Found: C, 65.50; H, 5.52 percent. Calc. for C₁₂H₁₂O₄; C, 65.46; H, 5.46 percent).

6-Methoxyindan-1-acetic acid (X)—IX (15 g) was reduced with zinc amalgam (50 g) and conc. HCl to give X in 70-75% yield with m. p. 97°-98°. (Found: C, 70.05; H, 6.80 percent. Calc. for C₁₂H₁₄O₃; C, 69.90; H, 6.80 percent).

5,6-Dimethoxyindan-3-one-1-acetic acid (XI)—Veratraldehyde (34 g; 0.2 mole) was treated with ethylacetoacetate (60 g; 0.43 mole) and piperidine (2.5 ml) at room temperature for 3 days to give ethyl 3,4-dimethoxybenzilidene bisacetoacetate in 85-90% yield. The solid bisester was crushed and washed with solvent ether. This bisacetoacetate (40 g) was dissolved in a hot solution of KOH (160 g in 120 ml of water) and refluxed with 80 ml of 90% alcohol for 1 hr. Then after removing alcohol and diluting with water, it was extracted with solvent ether. The aqueous layer was acidified with conc. HCl under cooling. The precipitated acid on crystallisation yielded 22g of the pure acid—having m. p. 188°-190°.

3, 4-Dimethoxyphenylglutaric acid (15g) was cyclised with PPA (225 g) either (i) by direct heating at 120° for 10 min or (ii) on boiling water bath for 4 hr with stirring. The keto acid (XI) was isolated by extracting with chloroform and crystallised from water. The yield was 65-70% having m. p. 175-177°. (Found: C, 62.50; H, 5.56 percent. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₄O₅; C 62.40; H, 5.60 percent).

5,6-Dimethoxyindan-1-acetic acid (XII)—XI was reduced with zinc amalgam (50g) and conc. HCl to give XII in 70-75% yield with m. p. 159.5-161° (Found: C, 66.32; H, 6.80 percent. Calc. for C₁₃H₁₆O₄; C, 66.10; H, 6.78 percent).

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